

“Blood Family” Activity With Respect To Comprehensive Guidance School Program

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Abstract—Children and adolescents developing in the worlds of today are facing a getting array of new and old challenges. School counselling is improving rapidly in contemporary education systems around the world. It can be said that counselling system in Turkey was newly borning. In this study, “Family of the Blood” activity is improved with respect to comprehensive guidance school program. The sample included 22 adolescents who were high school students. The activity was carried out in 4 sessions, each of which lasted 45 minutes. In the first session, students’ personal-social needs were determined. In the second session, in order to warm up, the students were asked three questions consisting of the constructional aspect. In the third session, the counselor and the teacher shared the results of students’ responses obtained in the previous session. In the fourth session, the tables formed by students were presented in the classroom. In order to evaluate the activity, three questions were asked of the teacher and counselor. According to the results, the lesson aims of curriculum and counselling aims of curriculum were attained. In the light of literature, the results were discussed and some suggestions were made. It is taken into consideration that the activity was beneficial in many respects, similar studies should be carried out in the near future.

Keywords—Comprehensive guidance program, education, family.

I. INTRODUCTION

CHILDREN and adolescents developing in the worlds of today are facing a getting array of new and old challenges for example violence in the home, school, and community; divorce; sexual experimentation are just a few examples. To know family and its functions is so important in order to solve these problems, and being healthy adult. In this context comprehensive guidance and its activities may help for children and especially adolescents. School counselling is improving rapidly in contemporary education systems around the world, and is increasing in number, and also improving in quality. Both school counselors and school counselling programs are affected by this improvement. One implication of these changes is that school counselling as a professional field needs to improve its programs and offerings in order to survive and have a stable position in educational systems. Comprehensive guidance programs and the activities based on these programs can be used as a cornerstone to achieve a stable position in school counselling and in contemporary educational systems.

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Why were comprehensive guidance programmes needed and why are they needed in contemporary education? The answers to these questions are in their historical context. The fact that comprehensive guidance programmes have a stable position in school counselling has not taken place suddenly ([1], [2], [3]). In this context, Sink [4] states that school counselling in USA has grown in three main stages. The first stage extends the cold war period. In this stage, school counselors were identified as the persons in the school who should test and identify students with academic talent as well as provide them encouragement and information about preparing for college and matriculating as science students. At second stage, Herr and Cramer [5] applied the concept of a systems approach to vocational guidance as a subsystem of guidance in more comprehensive terms and of education as the context for comprehensive guidance programs. According to Herr [5] counselling approaches in school neither result in positively nor present practical solutions to developmental problems. The economic recession that occurred in the USA in 1970s because of the Vietnam war caused some discussion about the efficacy of many institutions, including school systems. One aspect of the school systems that was debated was the efficacy of school counseling and it was in this context that guidance programs began to be developed. Career development theory and applications, accountability, accessibility and systems approaches were needed before comprehensive guidance programmes could emerge. The perception that individual counselling and counsellor-student interaction were not efficacious led to efforts to develop a more wholistic approach. Consequently, comprehensive guidance program including planning, arrangement, application and assesment started to be used in schools. After the 1980s, coinciding with the third stage, school counselors and career educators developed program-based approaches that incorporated a more systematic, preventive, educative and progressive vision of the place of school-based counseling in educational settings. Today, there is evidence that this programmatic approach has led to improved results [7].

It is important for school counselors to perform preferred guidance tasks. Because research evidence shows that positive changes occur when school counselors are performing preferred guidance tasks, thus providing guidance programs to be more fully implemented ([8], [9], [10]. Lapan, Gysbers, and Sun [6], found so many positive results when school counselors performed preferred guidance tasks. For instance, students had earned higher grades, their education was better preparing them for their future, their school made more career and college information available to them, and their school had a more positive climate. Likewise, Nelson and Gardner

[11], found that students rated their overall educational as better, took more advanced mathematics and science courses.

However, US was improving her own counselling systems during these periods, counselling system in Turkey was newly borning. When we looked at Turkish counselling system, the program based approach has been implemented since 2007. These programs don't completely fit the comprehensive guidance program. For instance, it doesn't include system supporting. It is constructed only based on activities of developmental periods for children and adolescents.

Comprehensive guidance programmes have common points in the aspects of their contents although they may be labeled differently in different countries and different cultures [12]. Such programs aim to satisfy the developmental needs of students in areas such as academic, career, personal and social development [13]. According to Gybers and Henderson [13], in the comprehensive guidance programmes, students are provided with information, skills, and attitudes that they will need in their lifelong career development. The term career means the roles, such as student, worker, consumer, citizen, and mother-father that the student will fill in home, school and society. These roles appear in having a job, pursuing a marriage, and in retirement. According to Gurman & Kniskern [14], the relationships between humans are designed via social codes. Family is a sub system of social systems. Family makes the child socialized by teaching these social codes. The function of family as the member of society has a constructive aspect. The presence of father, mother, brother, sister, wife-husband, son/daughter and their individual roles comprise a family system that functions as all members of the family carry out their necessary roles.

According to Papila, Olds and Feldman [15], adolescents start to spend most of their time outside the family as they grow older. This seems to accelerate adolescent social development. With identity development, adolescents become ready for the world of future adults [16]. With the development of sexual reproduction, the adolescent becomes a potential father or mother [17]. At this point, the adolescent needs to know the constructional aspect of family in order to have a healthy family life. Adolescents can learn the roles of individuals in a family in two different ways. The first way is social transfer or personal experience. The second one is to join constructed educational programs. In this context, in the direction of the aims of lesson and guidance curriculum, adolescents can gain insight into the constructional aspect of family by presenting the duties of blood cells.

Purpose of The Study

The main aim of this study is to actualize the "Family of Blood Activity" in the context of comprehensive guidance. There are two sub objectives of this study;

a) School counselling objective: To help students understand the roles and duties of individuals in a family.

b) Curriculum objective: To help students learn the elements of blood.

One of the important topics which a Vocational Health High (Nurse) School student should know is blood cells. Our body functions work via systems composed of organs. One of these systems is the circular system. The observable unit of circular system is blood cells. Blood cells are called erythrocytes, leucocytes, and platelets. Erythrocytes carry oxygen. Leucocytes defend the body against illnesses. And platelets are assigned in the process of coagulation of blood so they help stop bleeding. In one millimeter cube of blood there are approximately 4-5 billion of erythrocytes. The scarcity of erythrocyte is called anemia. In the case of anemia erythrocyte can not carry enough oxygen for cells. In one millimeter cube of blood there are approximately 7 billion leucocytes. If the number of leucocytes go up over 10 billion it is understood that there is a bacterial infection in the body. In one millimeter blood there are approximately 300,000 platelets. The scarcity of platelets is called thrombocytopenia and will result in coagulation problems [18].

II. METHOD

A. Participants

The activity was carried out in Pursaklar Vocational Health High School in Turkey. 22 students in grade 9, 4 of whom are male and 18 of whom are female participated in the study. The activity was carried out with the cooperation of the anatomy teacher and counselor of the school.

B. Instruments

A needs analysis questionnaire, which consisted of 10 questions about personal-social development, and are based on seven target behaviors was used to evaluate the activities. This instrument includes 10 open-ended yes-no questions such as "I know that there are responsibilities and tasks which everyone has to do in my family; I know that how people live in an accordance with their families.". The questionnaire has content validity but it doesn't have reliability, and this is the most important limitation of this study.

C. Process

The activity was carried out in 4 sessions, each of which lasted 45 minutes. The sessions are briefly explained below.

1. First Session:

In the first session, students' personal-social needs were determined. In order to do this, target behaviours related to acquisition domains were defined. The assessment indicated four acquisition domains with 7 target behaviours such as "to know and accept that the importance of home and family, and to improve that the sense of being a part of society defined [3]. After that, a needs analysis study was carried out. Students completed a needs analysis questionnaire, which consisted of 10 questions about personal-social development. The results were then analyzed. According to the results of the needs analysis, it was seen that 55 percent of the study group seemed sufficient about these domains.

2. Second Session

In order to warm up, the students were asked three questions consisting of the constructional aspect. In terms of curriculum three questions about the elements of blood were asked. The responses to these questions were analyzed by content analysis with respect to sentences.

3. Third Session

The counselor and the teacher shared the results of students' responses obtained in the previous session. After that, students were divided into three groups. The groups were asked to form a blood family, to find the similarities between the roles of members of family and functions of elements of blood. The students were asked to present the results in a table as a homework. The content of a sample table is given in Appendix-1.

4. Fourth Session

The tables formed by students were presented in the classroom. In order to evaluate the activity, three questions were asked of the teacher and counselor. The responses to these questions were analyzed by content analysis with respect to sentences and the activity was exhibited for a week in the school.

III. RESULTS

Results are based on an evaluation of Blood Family activity. In order to evaluate the activity, the teacher was asked three open-ended questions about whether the activity was beneficial and what can be done for better results. The responses of the students were analyzed. The results are given in Table-1 below.

TABLE 1 THE EVALUATION OF THE ACTIVITY

Activity was beneficial, because:	F
We learned the duties of blood cells and the members of a family.	10
2. The group study was beneficial	4
3 We made comparisons	4
4. To attribute with daily life easy the comprehension	3
5. Simulation helped us to understand	2
6. We learned that if we don't know these topics we can not succeed in the lesson	1
7. We learned that in order to compare, we need some information	1
8. We learned that we can not forget this activity	1
9. We understand the importance of family members	1
10. We understand the importance of family integrity.	1
11. We strengthen the things we know about these topics	1
12. To set connection between the topics enable us to have fresh and effective	1

In order to have a general evaluation, all of the students presented at least one reason for why they thought the activity

was beneficial. Although there were a variety of reasons given, some similar and some different all students agreed that the activity was beneficial. Students presented some suggestions for how to make the activity more beneficial. The suggestions are given in the Table-2

TABLE II THE SUGGESTIONS FOR BETTER ACTIVITY

Suggestions	F
1. I have no suggestions	9
2. We should hang on these activities on the bulletin board.	3
3. There should have been comprehensive researches	3
4. We should study and do more activities	2
5. Visual aids should have been implemented much	2
6. Presentations should have done individually	2
7. The time should have been lengthened	1

The teacher perceived the activity as beneficial. She stated that students expressed themselves and were more relaxed. On the other hand, she says that the process is quite relaxing and enjoyable for students. She expressed the view that the activity was important in order to reach the curriculum objectives.

IV. DISCUSSION

In this section, the results will be discussed in the light of literature and they will be evaluated, then some suggestions will be presented.

The whole activity is best understood in light of constructivist theory [19]. "Can knowledge be constructed without knowing the person?" This activity reminds us of the important point that the students constructed the knowledge. On the other hand, in the case of lecturing in traditional methods, teacher and student take their places in the classroom with the consciousness of responsibilities. The teacher is worried about transferring the topics related to the curriculum as quickly as possible. In this case, the level of readiness of the student that Piaget [20], stated is not questioned, and this prevents the knowledge taking place in the short-term and long-term memory in the aspect of information process approach [21]. That is to say, students become the transporter of the knowledge not the constructor of it. In fact, there are small-volume materials such as floppy disks to transport the knowledge. As a result, the activity is effective because it proves that students are important actors in constructing the information. In the view of teaching methods, this activity is beneficial. The connection made between knowledge and life enables students to learn easily.

In the point of student motivation, it can be seen that the students concretize the abstract knowledge. Concretization makes the topic suitable for the capability level. This situation helps the students to flow in the topic. This activity can be evaluated for intrinsic motivation. The fact that student is self-determined and autonomous [22] was an important factor. The activity enabled the student to be motivated intrinsically, thus satisfying the needs of belonging to the classroom, the group, and to the school.

In the view of counselling and lesson curriculum, generally students came to a better position in the acquisition domain in which they see themselves as sufficient. With this activity, students became conscious about constructional aspects of family, roles in family and their responsibilities. This consciousness was gained via the aim of curriculum. So, both the curricular aim and the aim of counselling were strengthened. By carrying out this activity, the counselor became closer to both teacher and the students. Therefore, the goals of counselor in the school were actualized.

On the basis of the results of the activity, some suggestions were indicated. If it is taken into consideration that the activity was beneficial in many respects, similar studies should be carried out in the near future. In order to develop such kinds of programs, some institutions in counselling research centers should be established. Thus, in a very short time data can be reached by systematic methods. Counselors in schools can contribute to develop the domain by trying to do activities together with the branch teachers.

APPENDIX-1 SAMPLE OF TABLE CONTEXT

GROUP NAME: "EIGHT SWORDSMAN GROUP: PUNISHMENT AND BLOOD FAMILIES"

Platelet and Child

We can simulate the children platelets. Because the duty of platelets is to coagulate the blood and prevent loss of blood. Similarly, childrens make a family enforced. For example; if there occurred a problem in the family, it could be overcome easily if there were a child in the family, and the members of the family would clamp together.

In the scarcity of platelets there occurs thrombocytopenia and if they are excessive thrombocytosis can be in the body. Similar to this, if a family is deprived of children, that family always feel the deprivation of a child. The responsibility of children is to obey the rules in the family and to try to be respectful to the father and mother.

Erythrocyte and Father

We can simulate erythrocyte a father. Because erythrocytes have the substance that makes the blood (the color) red. It is the main element of blood. It carries carbonhydrate and oxygen for blood. It is produced in red marrowbone. Likewise, a father in a family is the main member of the family. The one who maintains the family is father he is the pillar of a family. In the scarcity of erythrocyte and in the extreme amount of it there occur anaemia and poliglobuli respectively. If a family is deprived of the father, the children feel insufficient themselves in an aspect. They got worse in economicly. If a family is crowded family (with grandparents, many children or aunts, uncles etc.) rather than a nucleus one, the father of the family can not bear the whole burden. In the absence of the mother, the father and the children get upset. The order of the family breaks up.

Leucocyte and Mother

We can simulate leucocyte a mother because they function in the immune system in blood. They provide blood with

antibody. If immune system got worse, our strength against illnesses decreases. The duty of a mother is to arrange the Works in a family to communicate with the husband and the children and make the order in the family. If she can and carry out these responsibilities some certain needs of family can not be provided. There could be chaotic situation in the family. In the scarcity of leucocytes in blood more than necessary, leukocytosis is seen as illness.

REFERENCES

- [1] Doğan, S. (2000). Pratik bir sınıf rehberlik ve psikolojik danışma programı. *EğitimYönetim Dergisi*, 21, (6):140-225.
- [2] Erkan, S. (2001). *Rehberlik programlarının hazırlanması*. Ankara: Nobel Yayın Dağıtım.
- [3] Yesilyaprak, B.(2003). *Eğitimde rehberlik hizmetleri gelişimsel yaklaşım*. Ankara: Nobel Yayın Dağıtım.
- [4] Sink, C.(2002).). Comprehensive guidance and counseling programs and development of multicultural student-citizens. *Professional School Counseling*, 6, (2):130-137.
- [5] Herr, E.L. (2001). The impact of national policies, economics. *School Counseling*, 4 (4):236-246.
- [6] Lapan, R.T., Gysbers, N.C.,& Sun, Y.(1997). The impact of more fully implemented guidance programs on the school experiences of high school. a statewide evaluation study. *Journal Of Counseling And Development*, 75 (?): 292-302.
- [7] Borders, L. D., & Drury, S. M. (1992). Comprehensive school counseling programs: A review for policy makers and practitioners. *Journal of Counseling and Development*, 70, 487-498.
- [8] Gerler, E. R. (1985). Elementary school counseling research and the classroom learning environment. *Elementary School Guidance and Counseling*, 20, 39-48.
- [9] Lapan, R. T., Gysbers, N. C., Hughey, K., & Arni, T. J. (1993). Evaluating a guidance and language arts unit for high school juniors. *Journal of Counseling and Development*, 71, 444-452.
- [10] Nelson, D. E., & Gardner, J. L. (1998). An evaluation of the comprehensive guidance program in Utah public schools. Salt Lake City, UT: *The Utah State Office of Education*.
- [11] Watkins, C.(2001). Comprehensive guidance and counseling programs in an international context. *Professional School Counseling*, 4(4): 262-271.
- [12] Gysbers, N.C. & Henderson, P.(2000). *Developing and managing your school guidance program (3rd ed.)*. Alexandria, VA: ACA.
- [13] Gysbers, N.C. & Henderson, P.(2001). Comprehensive guidance and counseling programs: a rich history and a bright future. *Professional School Counseling*, 4, (4):246-257
- [14] Gurman, A.S., & Kniskern, D.P.(1981). *Handbook of family therapy*. New York: Brunner/Mazel Publishers.
- [15] Papalia, D.E., Olds, S.W., & Feldman, R.D. (2004). *Human development*. New York: Mc Graw Hill.
- [16] Erikson, E.H.(1968). *Identity: Youth and crisis*. New York: Norton
- [17] Özden, M.(1999). *Fizyoloji*. Ankara: Songür Yayıncılık.
- [18] Solomon, E.P.(2003). *İnsan anatomisi ve fizyolojisine giriş* (Çev.L.B. Süzen).İstanbul:Birol Basın Yayın Dağıtım.
- [19] Tuncer, C.(2004). *Yabancı dil olarak ingilizce öğretmenlerinin yetiştirilmesinde kuram ve uygulama boyutuyla oluşturmaya yaklaşım*. (Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). İstanbul: İstanbul Üniversitesi SosyalBilimler Enstitüsü. Bowen, M.(1990). *Family therapy in clinical practice*. New York: Jason Aronson.
- [20] Piaget, J.(1970). *Science of education and psychology of the child*. New York: Viking Press.
- [21] Bjorklund, D.F.(2000). *Children thinking*. US: Wadsworth.
- [22] Deci, E.L., & Ryan, R.M.(1985). *Intrinsic motivation and self determination in human behavior*. New York: Plenum.